

Charisma Decision-Making And Its Relationship To Managing Psychological Stress Among Volleyball Players In Volleyball In Iraq

Aqeel Jareh Sabr, Mohammed Rahim Fail, Raja Abdulsamad Ashoor

Article Info	Abstract
<p>Article History</p> <p>Received: April 07, 2021</p> <p>Accepted: June 06, 2021</p> <hr/> <p>Keywords : Volleyball, The Operational , Research Community</p> <p>DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.4904761</p>	<p><i>The research problem lies in the idea that the quality of how decisions are made depends on how stress is assessed and interpreted, and what coping and self-regulatory strategies the athlete applies in an effort to maintain the operational efficiency of the mathematical cognitive system, as athletes make critical decisions that are immediately examined by fans and the means the media, as it is often evaluated based on the outcome and not on the intention of choosing them. The researchers used the descriptive approach in the survey method, which is the method used by researchers to obtain adequate and accurate information depicting the social reality that affects all activities. The research community included club players to an excellent degree. For volleyball in Iraq, which numbered (150) players representing (14) clubs, the research sample consisted of (100) players, meaning (66.66%). There are multiple levels of charisma in decision-making and management of psychological stress for volleyball players, and the most important recommendations are the adoption of these two tools to measure the charisma of decision-making and WADA the psychological pressure of volleyball players.</i></p>

Introduction

Decision-making is an essential element in any sport, especially the activities of open, fast and dynamic team sports such as volleyball, football, handball and basketball, and in order to succeed in winning any game and competition, whether at the national or international level and in all individual and team sports, as there is a need To review all success factors in order to make a better winning decision, especially at the level of elite sport activities. It appears that coaches and athletes consistently make good decisions in situations that are temporarily severely restricted. Usually, the decision-making process occurs during interaction with the external environment or internal desires and requirements. In sports groups, it can work slowly under conditions that lack environmental restrictions and requirements, but it must be fast under conditions of stress, stress, or time constraints, where when conditions permit the athlete's brain processes the information needed to make decisions intentionally through an association Cognitive mathematical, and specifically under conditions of psychological stress, the perceptual-sensory system stops working properly and the likelihood of making a wrong decision increases. All is large, so stress management must be taken into account.

2- Research problem:

Competitive sporting events are full of psychological, social and emotional pressures. The processing of information under pressure may be affected by the lack of this attention, which prevents the identification and selection of the signals of the basic sports environment. In contrast, the cognitive mathematical system has limited resources to create meaningful visual patterns and initiate a response, and instead of Thus, the cognitive mathematical system becomes burdened with overlapping ideas, and attempts to control emotions are accompanied by a decline in self-efficacy. Under these stressful conditions, mathematical decision-making is expected to suffer due to the inability to create and stimulate the appropriate response, and this in turn is likely to lead to Decreased performance, and the existing evidence supports the idea that the quality of how decisions are made depends on how stress is assessed and interpreted, and what coping and self-regulatory strategies the athlete applies in an effort to maintain the operational efficiency of the mathematical cognitive system, as athletes make critical decisions that are examined immediately from By fans and the media, as it is often evaluated based on outcome rather than on the intention of their choice, and how they balance Wen is among the art and science of decision making, as the broad technical knowledge of the athletes in their field may not be sufficient to win the game.

3- Research aims:

- 1- Building and codifying a survey, charisma, decision-making and psychological stress management for volleyball players in Iraq.

- 2- Knowing the relationship between the charismas of decision-making and managing the psychological stress of volleyball players in Iraq.

4- Research fields:

- 1- The human field: for the premium class volleyball players in Iraq for the 2020-2021 sports season
- 2- Time domain: 10/20/2020 until 2/10/2021
- 3- Spatial domain: stadiums and club sports halls in Iraq.

3- Research methodology and field procedures:

Research Methodology

The researchers used the descriptive approach using the survey method, which is the method used by the researchers in obtaining adequate and accurate information depicting the social reality that affects all activities (132: 3).

The research community and its sample: It is all the individuals who are the subject of the problem. Thus, the research community included the players of clubs of the excellent degree of volleyball in Iraq, whose number is (150) players representing (14) clubs and the research sample consisted of (100) players, meaning (66.66) %).

Field research procedures:

1. Procedures for building a questionnaire, charisma, decision-making and psychological stress management: In order to reach the results of the current research, its objectives must be achieved, which is building a questionnaire, charisma, decision-making and psychological stress management for volleyball players. For the purpose of achieving this, the researchers followed the following steps:
2. Determining the objective of the scale: The goal of building the two measuring tools is to identify the charisma of decision-making and manage the psychological stress of volleyball players in Iraq.
3. Preparing the initial formula for the two measurement tools: The researchers drafted (30) paragraphs for a questionnaire for the charisma of decision making that are compatible with the nature and purpose of the measurement and (35) items for the stress management scale.

Presenting the initial formula for the two scales to the arbitrators:

After the experts and specialists expressed their responses and observations on the paragraphs of the scale, it appeared that the paragraphs agreed upon by (75%) or more experts and specialists are considered acceptable, that is, by (12) experts out of (16) experts, and the final analysis resulted in the acceptance of (27) paragraphs. The questionnaire for the charisma of decision-making and (32) paragraphs for the questionnaire of stress management. The validity of the peace was confirmed after presenting it to experts with five alternatives (always, often, rarely, sometimes, never), noting that the paragraphs were formulated in positive and negative directions and weight was given to paragraphs (1-5).

Procedures for building the two questionnaires: Then the researchers distributed the two forms to the sample of (100) players, and after completing the process of distributing the forms and answering them, the researchers checked each form to ensure that all the paragraphs were answered correctly.

Analysis of paragraphs statistically:

First: The strength of paragraph discrimination: Distinguishing power is defined as the ability of the paragraph to distinguish between individuals who obtain high scores and individuals who obtain low scores in the trait measured by the scale (258: 8).

For the purpose of finding the discriminatory strength of the paragraphs after obtaining the sample answers for the two tools, the (T-Test) test was used for the purpose of distinguishing, and after comparing the error ratio of the corresponding to (T) calculated, it was found that there were (3) paragraphs whose values were greater than (0.05), which indicates that they are not Distinctive, therefore, it was excluded (15,21,5) from the charisma decision-making questionnaire, and the number of its paragraphs became (24) paragraphs. As for the psychological stress management questionnaire, by following the same steps, (2) paragraphs (16,7) were excluded and the number of its paragraphs became (30) Paragraph.

Second: Internal consistency: The correlational relationship between the total score and the degree of each paragraph of the scale was extracted using the internal consistency method using the Pearson correlation coefficient by the statistical program (ssps) to find out the extent of the paragraph's relevance to the field to which it belongs. Accordingly, (2) paragraphs were excluded from the questionnaire. The charisma of decision-making, and the scale consisted of (22) items. As for the stress management questionnaire, (6) items were excluded, and the scale consisted of (24) items.

Scientific Transactions of Adatine:

For the purpose of obtaining the stability of the two scales, the researchers used two methods, the half segmentation and Vachronbach, and the researchers used the Pearson correlation coefficient to identify the correlation relationship, as it reached the charisma decision-making questionnaire (0.793) and the stress management questionnaire (0.801). Spearman Brown's Law, and the result was for the charisma decision-making questionnaire (0.845) and for the stress management questionnaire (0.795). Therefore, the two tools are stable.

Truthfulness: The truthfulness of the test is intended "to be an honest test when it measures the purpose for which it was set." (53: 1). And honesty consists of several types, and the researchers used the following types:

Apparent honesty: The experts agreed that these paragraphs are easy to formulate and clear, and they agree by (75%) or more than it is sufficient because they measure what they were prepared for.

Construct validity: which is sometimes called the sincerity of the concept and is considered one of the most appropriate types of honesty because it depends on the experimental verification of the extent to which the scores of the paragraphs correspond to the characteristic or concept to be measured, so this type of honesty has been achieved through the use of discriminatory power and internal consistency.

Objectivity of the scale: Objectivity means that the subjectivity of the researchers, their opinions and beliefs do not interfere with the test results completely (202: 4) and since the scale contains the key to correction, it is considered objective.

Torsion coefficient: To find out how close or far the sample is to the normal distribution, the researchers calculated the torsion coefficient, as its value reached (0.49) for the charisma decision-making questionnaire and (0.72) for the stress management questionnaire.

Standard levels: The researchers chose five levels that were distributed naturally for the building sample of (100) as follows (very good, good, average, acceptable, weak) and it appeared to us that the sample occurred in the medium level.

Statistical methods: The researchers used the Statistical Package (SPSS) Sixteenth Edition. Presentation, analysis and discussion of results:

Presenting, analyzing, and discussing the results of the openness to experience scale

Table (1) shows the arithmetic mean and standard deviations of the two research tools

the level	±P	S	Ada t search
Average	14.26	67.2	Charisma decision-making questionnaire
Average	15.23	74.3	Psychological stress management questionnaire

Table (2) it shows the standard and raw levels and scores and the percentage of the two search tools

Percentage Percentage	the number	Grades rough	Standard grades	Levels
				Charisma make the decision
%12	12	93-110	68-80	very good
%20	20	76-92	56-67	good
%45	45	59-75	44-55	Average
%15	15	42-58	32-43	Acceptable
%8	8	-41and below	20-31	Weak
				Managing psychological stress
%10	10	102-120	68-80	very good
%22	22	84-101	57-68	good
%48	48	65-83	45-56	Average
%11	11	47-64	33-44	Acceptable
%9	9	-46and below	20-32	Weak

Through Table (2) it is evident that the sample obtained a medium level, as the researchers see this result suitable for the players in that some players focus their attention on aspects and neglect the other aspects, as the issue of decision-making is very important and the players need a high degree of objectivity and ability. To make the right decisions as well as the urgent need for real knowledge of the obstacles that enter as a model for the training process, so the objective side is not given its right. The decisions made by the player will be far from maturing and do not achieve effective solutions, as the decision-making process is one of the most dangerous tasks facing the player and who He must be aware of identifying the problem and the challenges posed by the situation variables and the decision-making environment represented by the number and quality of people affected by the decision, the quantity and quality of information available, and how to address it. This is confirmed by Marwan Abdel Majeed (2015). In the event that the real problem is not known, the decision that will be taken will be an incorrect decision. For not being fit with the problem in which he was issued (109: 6)

2-3 Presenting, analyzing and discussing the results of the link between the two research tools

Table (3) shows the mean, standard deviation, and r value of the two measures

mistake percentage	Value (t)	Managing psychological stress		Charisma make the decision	
		±p	s	±p	s
0.000	704.0	15.23	74.3	14.26	67.2

Table (3) shows that there is a significant correlation between the two research tools of volleyball players, and the researchers attribute that to the fact that the decision-making process is not an easy process, because the problems facing decision-makers are many and complex, including what is related to the self-formation of the decision-maker, including what is It is linked to the environment and the environment with all its opportunities, relationships, general goals, traditions, etc., and this was confirmed by NawafKanaan (2012) that the approaches and methods of decision-makers are influenced by personal factors stemming from their personalities and that the most important of these factors are their attitudes, values, scientific level, previous experiences, pattern of behavior and social backgrounds, and that these The characteristics differ from one person to another, and the researchers believe that psychological stress is one of the issues affecting the players. The state of stress experienced by the player has become a familiar and common thing in the sports environment due to what the player is exposed to during training and various sports competition, which in turn affects the player internally and on his external behavior, whether It was with his dealings with other players or the sporting environment surrounding him in general, such as the coach, the administrator and the media, so we see that the players who own The ability to make decisions will be motivated in their practical behavior and thus their ability to perform optimally and under the various psychological pressures they are exposed to, and this is confirmed by Muhammad Ibrahim (2016). The decisions taken by the individual are most often affected by the behavioral and personal characteristics of him when identifying the problem and making a decision. About her (65: 2)

4- Conclusions and recommendations

4.1- Conclusions

- 1- The two current questionnaires are considered a tool to reveal the level of decision-making and manage psychological stress of volleyball players
- 2- The emergence of multiple levels in the level of charisma in decision-making and managing the psychological stress of volleyball players
- 3- The highest percentage obtained by players within the levels for the two questionnaires was average.

4.2- Recommendations

- 1- Adopting these two tools to measure the charisma of decision-making and manage the psychological stress of volleyball players.
- 2- The necessity for clubs to provide equal opportunities for their players by holding scientific meetings and field visits to model clubs in order to communicate for more openness, harmony and awareness of them.
- 3- Conducting a study of the charisma of decision-making and its relationship to some other psychological skills and some personality traits.

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Author Information

Asst. Prof. Dr. AqeelJareh Sabr

College of Physical Education and Sports Sciences,
Basra University, Iraq

Asst. Prof. Dr. Mohammed Rahim Fail

College of Physical Education and Sports Sciences,
Basra University, Iraq

Asst. Prof. Dr. Raja Abdulsamad Ashoor

College of Physical Education and Sports Sciences,
Basra University, Iraq
